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FORMING THE SKILLS OF INDEPENDENT ANALYSIS OF WORKS OF
ART OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Abstract: ART technology is the basis of forming the knowledge and skills of primary school students in the arts. This article describes the situations that should be paid attention to when forming the ability of independent analysis of works of art of elementary school students.

Keywords: ART, painting, technology, music.

The advancement of techniques and technologies in the course of the development of humanity today requires the formation of the aesthetic taste, consciousness and culture of a person at the level of demand. Because the development of techniques and technologies creates technocratic thinking in the mind of a person, i.e. the weakening of the sense of beauty and, on the contrary, the priority of reality. For this reason, pedagogues are paying special attention to shaping the minds of learners and developing their creative thinking skills with the help of ART technology. Regarding this issue, special pedagogical disciplines have been established in our country, one of them is the educational discipline "ART, technology and creativity". Formation of professional competencies of future elementary school teachers in the process of higher pedagogical education with the help of this subject is one of the important tasks.

ART technology is of practical importance as one of the important foundations of forming the knowledge and skills of elementary school students in the arts. Because this issue is determined by:

Implementation of aesthetic education of elementary school students with the help of ART technology;

1. Developing art skills of elementary school students using ART technology;
2. Development of the creative approach of elementary school students with the help of ART technology.

Today, elementary school students widely use educational and technical tools such as computers. Especially, they have the opportunity to get a lot of new information by means of a computer. Therefore, the importance of ART technology in weakening the content of technocratic thinking in them is important. Because ART technology has the ability to form the speech culture of primary school students through speech art, their aesthetic feelings through musical art, and their aesthetic taste through descriptive art. In this regard, it is especially important to develop students' skills in reading, choosing music, and analyzing examples of fine art. Because book reading is the basis of speech art of ART technology,

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the ability to choose music is an important basis of music art, and examples of fine art determine the educational importance of this art. Therefore, in the process of technological development, education of elementary school students using the basics of ART technology is of great practical importance.

The fact that elementary school students are in the process of development is precisely the result of education with the help of technologies such as ART. In this regard, primary school students' enjoyment of words and their meanings, inspiration from the aesthetic effect of music, and aesthetic inspiration from examples of fine art are important components of the educational process. Today, primary education experts are interested in the problem that students live in an extremely wide world of information and receive it directly. The availability of various information in the world of information requires wide use of the capabilities of educational tools such as ART technology. Because such technologies protect elementary school students from inappropriate nervousness, depression, and self-doubt. On the contrary, it serves as an important tool in the formation of their qualities.

Art is a broad concept. After all, art is the things created, brought into being, and created by human labor, intellect, perception, and consciousness. Art is a creative type of human activity, and each work of art shows the unique talent of a person. And finally, art is closely related to human skill. Art, in a broad sense, includes artistic values, their creation (artistic creation) and consumption (artistic perception) processes. Art has developed in connection with the development of mankind until the present time. Images of animals carved on rocks found in Uzbekistan, Spain, the Sahara and a number of other ancient countries have a sophisticated value even from the point of view of the current era. These monuments were the results of the sophisticated work of man, whose buds of artistic activity were just beginning to appear.

Art has always satisfied social needs in the process of historical development. Art is related to the complex, rank-and-file relations of social life, and it is at the same time a special type of labor, a special field of social production, a form of social consciousness, a specific field of knowledge, and acts as a form of creative activity. Art is an independent sphere of social life, and according to its specific legal functions, it represents a separate social unit. Art affects all aspects of society, connects with all forms of social consciousness, encourages people to be active in various aspects of life.

There are many intermediary nations that connect art and social life. any artistic phenomenon - whether it is a specific work or a stylistic direction, they are determined, evaluated, measured by the level of influence of religious and moral practices in their creation and development.

The relative independence of art development is explained by the fact that the level of artistic development of society does not always correspond to the level of its economic development. The development or decline of art, its one or another type, the vivid expression of its appearance, definitely depends on the nature of social relations, the ratio

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of certain group forces, the characteristics of ideological life, and the status of a person in society. For example, the development of the art of the ancient world was determined by the coincidence of a number of conditions and factors and the creation of a very favorable situation. The relatively independent functioning of art in the life of society is also related to the manifestation of the law of inheritance. Succession is not a phenomenon unique to art. It applies to all forms of social consciousness. Succession is more manifested in the spheres of political and legal consciousness, which are related to the material basis of society.

Succession exists in all aspects of life, spiritual life. However, in art, which is far from the economic ground, covering all aspects of life, inheritance is manifested in a bright, full, comprehensive way. All aspects of art - thematic direction, ideological and spiritual rules and tones, creative beliefs, style, types and forms of expressive means are especially exaggerated by succession.

As in other forms of social consciousness, knowledge and ideology are interwoven and interconnected in art. At different historical stages and in different forms of art, knowledge and ideology work in mutual proportion. The role of art in the cognitive process is clearly visible in the medium of fiction. When art is viewed as a separate type of knowledge, it is usually based on works of fiction. It is known that the ability of music to know and understand is somewhat limited compared to fiction, but music is of great importance in perceiving reality in the spirit of special subtlety, sensitivity, and sincerity. Architecture performs a similar task. Architecture, which is an art form related to satisfying people's needs, reflects the characteristics and signs of the era, people's everyday life, tastes and dreams, hopes and dreams.

Art, like science, has incomparable knowledge and understanding, even if it is within its own subject. But the process of artistic knowledge and understanding of art takes place within its own characteristics. Art helps to perceive reality in a more full-blooded and attractive way through artistic means.

For art, a person is the main subject in the form of a single, rare, irrevocable individual, interconnected and intertwined in terms of all his biological, spiritual, social-group, national-ancestral and purely individual signs and characteristics. Art is able to cover all the attractive wealth and beauty of reality. This reality should be expressed as a reflection of the basic needs and interests of a person who has become a social person.

No matter how important science and technology are in human life, art cannot have a priority status. In art, science serves as a symbol of human activity created for people. If the scientific-technical, ecological, management problems, feelings, and meaning are deprived of the environment, there will be no art. Art is alive with emotions and feelings, it has the power to influence, teach, and educate.

Man is not always directly represented in art. For example, the human figure is not represented in the landscape or still life type of art. This does not mean that man is not reflected in these works of art. The image of the landscape shows the most delicate and

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attractive aspects of human feelings. For example, through the scenic works of artists such as Hrol Tansikboev, Ne'mat Koziboev, Rahim Akhmedov, Rozi Choriev, bright sadness, carefree joy, anxious passion, upbeat spirit, life-giving dreams - hopes, creativity and sense of creation in a person. evokes feelings. In these works, people are aroused by emotions and various experiences, and by influencing the human mind and soul, art and human integrity and harmony emerge.

The still-life type of fine art consists mostly of images of inanimate objects - fruits, flowers, food, drinks, and although we do not see a person's reflection in them, we understand that the subject of these works is still about a person and his life. Looking at the images of a glass, a crumpled table, and spilled oil in the still life "Breakfast with Somsa" by the Dutch artist Willem Heda, we see not only the level of the glass, the quality of the table, the spilled oil from carelessness. , but we clearly feel the warm breath of a person, his hands touching this landscape. Finally, we are gripped by a kind of anxiety created by sensing the human drama that has just taken place.

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